

UNIVERSITI MALAYA

**FACULTY OF EDUCATION
PIX2007 EDUCATION & RESEARCH
INDIVIDUAL ASSIGNMENT**

TASK 1: CONTEMPORARY EDUCATIONAL ISSUES (CLO1)

*Handwriting vs. Digital Note-Taking:
The Trade-Off Between Efficiency and Cognitive Depth*

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1.0 Introduction

The use of electronic devices for note-taking is increasing among students (Flanigan et al., 2024). Devices such as laptops and tablets are rapidly replacing the good old pens and paper as primary note-taking tools in modern classrooms. While digital notes indeed have their unique advantages, most journal articles concur that such a modern method tends to lean more towards the negative than the positive.

The problems are discussed thoroughly in the chosen articles. As educators, it is important for us to anticipate these seemingly small issues to ensure effective learning outcomes for students across the nation.

2.0 Search Strategy

For this report, I turned to Google Scholar to find the necessary journal articles. In the search box, I entered several keywords that are related to the topic of discussion. Those keywords include:

- Digital note-taking
- Digital notes vs handwritten
- Impact of digital note-taking

Subsequently, I was presented with a lot of related articles. I only needed five for the report; thus, I began filtering them out one by one. Anything published prior to the year 2000 was excluded, and I eventually got what I came for.

3.0 Local & Global Significance

46% of surveyed teachers reported that students tend to be careless when taking notes digitally, while the other 40% reported that the written notes with the use of such devices often contain poor spelling and grammatical errors (Kruse et al., 2023). Not only that, but the constant transition between note-taking applications also tends to delay and disturb the writing process (Kruse et al., 2023).

Moreover, the use of electronic devices more often than not leads to multitasking problems. With access to the internet, students are more likely to surf through unrelated websites during lectures. They would not focus in class, hence leaving them with nothing more but an empty digital note (Stacy & Cain, 2015).

In free recall tasks, those who write notes by hand outperform those who type (Aragón-Mendizábal et al., 2016). Not only in those, but the students who write notes by hand generally perform better academically (Flanigan et al., 2024). This is due to more personalised notes, deeper cognitive processing and active paraphrasing, which enhance understanding and long-term memory retention. While digital notes allow for a snappier note-taking process, they risk becoming overly verbatim. The students may get all the words jotted down, but not the meaning behind each of them.

These studies, coupled with many others, show that digital note-taking does indeed leave a significant negative impact on students' performances. If this persists, we may witness one of the most notable declines in learning quality ever in history.

4.0 Discussion of Trends, Debates and Implications

Despite the overwhelming evidence of the drawbacks associated with digital note-taking, there are still arguments supporting its effectiveness in certain contexts. Human cognitive capabilities are limited when it comes to storing memory. While notebooks can act as an external memory storage space themselves, they are still limited to the number of pages that they have. Devices such as laptops and tablets, on the other hand, are far more flexible. It allows information to be stored in one place, making it more convenient overall. This encourages the potential of personal knowledge management systems, such as "Second Brain", that many young students today rely on (Kruse et al., 2023). Research also shows that those who use digital note-taking gather more information than those who write due to the lesser physical and cognitive effort required for typing. This makes revisions way more likely for students.

These arguments are not merely theoretical, either. Students who write in second language shows immense improvement in text length, spelling accuracy, and overall structure with the help of digital tools (Dahlström & Boström, 2017). For what it's worth, the finding is indeed a relief for those who write digitally.

That being said, these arguments do little to nothing to influence the choice of the students. Good or bad, the use of technology in note-taking is inevitable nonetheless. The trend shows between 25% to 50% of students now use laptops to improve their organization and review processes (Flanigan et al., 2024). Perhaps it is the fear of missing out, but it is safe to say that reliance on technology is not decreasing anytime soon.

5.0 Conclusion

Whether one method of taking notes is better than the other can be situational. However, based on the studies covered in the chosen journal articles, it is not as a black-and-white matter as some would like it to be. Of course, digital note-taking is the future of education. Ignoring its advantages would be unwise. Regardless, students must not abandon handwriting entirely to ensure their motor skills and cognitive development are always intact (Dahlström & Boström, 2017). Balance is the key.

References

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Appendix

Google Scholar

scholar.google.com/schhp?hl=en&as_sdt=0.5

Impact of digital note taking
digital note taking
digital notes vs handwritten

EN Privacy Terms Help

digital notes vs handwritten

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Review articles

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Digital note-taking: Discussion of evidence and best practices
JA Grahame - The Journal of Physician Assistant Education, 2016 - journals.lww.com
... laptops, tablets, and other **digital** devices over **handwritten notes** during lecture. Certainly, this ... of **digital** versus **handwritten note-taking** and offers suggestions for improved **digital note-**...
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... Although 89.2 percent of students in our sample agreed with the statement that **handwritten notes** are associated with better quiz and exam performance, not one student who primarily ...
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REVIEW

Note-taking and Handouts in The Digital Age

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